

New examples of not yet identified hijacked journals.

A brief investigation

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Abstract

The phenomenon of hijacked journals can be seen as the ultimate example of predatory publishing. Though there are some initiatives to list such sad examples of fraudulent practices it is out of personal experience that from time-to-time new examples ‘pop-up’. On numerous occasions, while participating on ResearchGate unfortunate experiences are shared. This report is an attempt to keep up to date in listing new examples of hijacked or cloned journals.

Introduction

Publishing in peer reviewed journals is considered the standard when it comes to science. Traditionally this has been in the hands of dedicated publishers. With the ever-extending possibilities of our computers and the world wide web a new publishing model is introduced, the open access model [1-3]. Nowadays ‘everyone’ with some basic knowledge about building a website can start their own journal or even ‘publishing house’. This potentially dangerous situation led to a seemingly unregulated growth of new journals and publishers led to worries about fake and fraudulent. Round 2010 a librarian called Jeffrey Beall started his crusade against what he called predatory journals, see for example [4]. Since the introduction of his list “the Beall’s list” it is basically used as to blacklist journals and publishers and is criticised as well [5-10]. However, while the term ‘predatory’ is subject to quite some debate, there is no discussion about a what

one might consider a sub-set of these journals, the hijacked journals. For more background see elsewhere [11, 12]. While participating in ResearchGate I came across numerous examples of victims of these (recent) hijacked journals. These examples triggered the here presented attempt to come up with recent not (yet) listed examples of hijacked journals.

Method

As indicated above, the examples listed were found while using ResearchGate and is the result of collecting examples over the last two years. The known examples were (as much as possible, since some of these lists are updated) excluded. Known examples of hijacked journals can be found in basically three sources: <https://predatoryjournals.com/hijacked/> , <https://beallslist.net/hijacked-journals/> and <https://ugccare.unipune.ac.in/Apps1/User/> .

Results

The findings are summarized and listed in Table 1. Unfortunately, in most cases the original website could not be traced. Therefore only the info of the hijacked (or cloned) version of the journals are indicated. For the most updated version of the list, I refer to:

https://www.researchgate.net/post/New_very_misleading_type_of_scam_Anyone_wit_h_recent_examples

Conclusion

The aim of this report is to warn researchers. It is by no means claiming to be complete. As indicated only examples of hijacked journals are included that were discussed or came up in Q & A of ResearchGate. Still, it might be an appreciated attempt as a source with additional examples not yet included in already existing sources.

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Table 1: New identified examples of hijacked journals

In alphabetic order:

Fake journal	Fake site
Adalya journal	http://www.adalyajournal.com/
Asia Life Sciences	http://emtpub.com/ (real journal seems to be discontinued. See for more examples of fake websites for this journal: the posts at the related SCImago site)
Informatica	http://www.informaticajournal.com/
International Medical Journal	https://www.seronijihou.com/
International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology	http://sersec.org/journals/index.php/ijast
JAC: A Journal of Composition Theory (journal is discontinued in 2014)	http://www.jctjournal.com/
Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University	http://jsju.org/index.php/journal
Journal of Xi'an Shiyou University, Natural Science Edition	https://www.xisdxjxsu.asia/
Journal of Xidian University	http://www.xadzkjdx.cn/
Liño	http://linojournal.com/
Opcion not safe to open!)	http://www.scieloopcion.com (according to my computer
Ponte	https://www.pontejournal.online/
Ponte: Multidisciplinary Journal of Sciences & Research	http://www.pontejournal.net/
Solid State Technology	http://solidstatetechnology.us/index.php/JSST
Tathapi	https://www.santpublications.com/ugc.php
TEST: Engineering & Management	http://www.testmagazine.biz/ *
*(real journal seems to be discontinued see also: https://www.researchgate.net/post/Test_Engineering_and_Management)	